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SHARQ MATEMATIK OLIMLARI VA ULARNING ASARLARIDA ARIFMETIKANING RIVOJLANISHI

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada Markaziy Osiyo tarixida siyosiy aql-idrok bilan ma'naviy jasoratni, diniy dunyoqarash bilan qomusiy bilimdonlikni o'zida mujassam etgan buyuk matematik olimlarning asarlaridagi arifmetikaga oid qarashlar tahlil qilinadi. Muhammad ibn Muso al Xorazmiy, Umar Xayyom, Nasriddin Tusiy, Jamshid Giyosiddin al - Koshiy, Ulug'bek va boshqa ko'plab buyuk ajdodlarimiz o'z asarlarida matematikaga oid qimmatli ma'lumotlar aks etgan. Ularning nomlari, jahon sivilizatsiyasi taraqqiyotiga qo'shgan buyuk hissalari hozirgi kunda butun dunyoga ma'lum.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: arifmetika, algebra, mutafakkir, algoritm, madaniyat, sivilizatsiya, madrasa, tarix, ilm-fan, rasadxona

РАЗВИТИЕ АРИФМЕТИКИ У ВОСТОЧНЫХ МАТЕМАТИКОВ И ИХ ТРУДОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ: в истории Центральной Азии было немало великих деятелей, сочетавших в себе политическую мудрость и духовное мужество, религиозное мировоззрение и энциклопедические знания. Изучены труды Мухаммада ибн Мусы аль-Хорезми, Умара Хайяма, Насридина Туси, Джамшида Гиёсиддина аль-Коши, Улугбека и многих других великих предков. известен всему миру. Будем знакомиться со статьями

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: арифметика, алгебра, мыслитель, алгоритм, культура, цивилизация, медресе, история, наука, обсерватория.

DEVELOPMENT OF ARITHMETIC IN EASTERN MATHEMATICIANS AND THEIR WORKS

ABSTRACT In this article, in the history of Central Asia, there were many great figures who combined political wisdom and spiritual courage, religious worldview and encyclopedic knowledge. The works of Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi, Umar Khayyam, Nasriddin Tusi, Jamshid Giyosiddin al-Koshi, Ulugbek and many other great ancestors have been studied. Their names and their great contributions to the development of world civilization are now known to the whole world. We will get acquainted with their works.

KEY WORDS: arifmetic, algebra, thinker, algorithm, culture, civilization, madrasa, history, science, observatory

Muhammad al Khorezmi a scholar who made an invaluable contribution to the development for world science and made great discoveries. The bibliographical data had not been found. But, there are the facts that at the beginning of 800's he was invited to Ma'mun ibn Haruna ar-Rashid court, the Baghdad Caliph's viceroy in Khorasan, and by twenty years old he was well-known scientist, got his education in native Khorazm. In 813 Ma'mun took the throne and together with his scholars that he had gathered around him in Marv moved to Bagdad. Ma'mun was a fan of science. Here, he had founded Bayt al Hikma (The House of Wisdom), at the history of science it was

named as "Baghdad academy" or "Ma'mun Academy". Muhammad al Khorazmi was the leader of scientific center to the end of his life. A lot of scholars and scientists from different parts of Central Asia and Arabian East worked there. The richest library of old manuscripts was at their disposal. The observatory had been constructed for works and discoveries. The Khorezmian palace created a blessing and took an active part in the first academy of the East ("Bayt-ul-Hikmat ") "House of the Wise". Although Khorezmi created many works, not all of them have reached us. Khorezmi's works on arithmetic and algebra opened a new era in the history of mathematics, the era of

medieval mathematics, and made a great contribution to the development of mathematics in the following centuries. Pupils have often heard the words algebra and algorithm. Algebra is a large part of mathematics, and algorithm is the main term of modern calculation techniques and mathematics. The words algebra and algorithm are related to the name of mathematician, astronomer and geographer, "the father of modern algebra" al-Khorazmi. His treatise "Al-jabr wal-muqabala" was later called "algebra" in Europe. Due to this work, the term "algorithm" appeared in the name of Al-Khorazmi at the beginning of the 12th century. Khorezmi's works on mathematics have been translated into Western and Eastern languages and have served as a guide for many centuries. Khorezmi's works on "Indian calculation and numbers", "Al-Jabr", "Arithmetic", "About the marble clock", "The image of the earth", "The book of history", "Jewish eras and holidays" are especially known and famous. His work called "Zizhi" as the first astronomical work, did a great service for the development of this science not only in the East, but also in the West. Muhammad ibn Musa Khorezmi's exemplary life, work, creations, legacy are priceless wealth and have not lost their value and importance.

Muhammad Taragai Ulugbek was born in 1394 in Sultanate, Iran. Ulugbek is a great Uzbek scientist and statesman. He is the grandson of Timur (1336-1405). Ulugbek's father Shahrukh (1377 - 1447) was also a statesman. His real name is Muhammed Taragai. In 1409, Sohrukh established two

independent states instead of his father's state. One is the center of Khorasan, Herat, and the other is Samarkand, the center of Movaraunnahr (administration). Khiorot was directed by Shahrukh himself. And he entrusted the management of Movarounnahr to Ulugbek. Unlike his grandfather Timur, Ulugbek did not like military campaigns. He would march against him only if it was absolutely necessary, if a khan violated the borders of his state. He was more interested in science, construction, improvement of cities and villages. He built a madrasa in Bukhara in 1447, in Samarkand in 1490, and in Gijduvon in 1432-1433. He completed the construction of "Bibikhanim" mosque, "Gori-Amir" mausoleum and "Shohi Zinda". Around 1425-1428, he built his own observatory on the Obi Rahmat hill near Samarkand. The building of the observatory was 3-storeyed, and the height of its main weapon was about 50 meters. Ulug Bek's interest in science was first of all his trips to other countries with his grandfather Timur, his conversations with poets and scientists in his grandfather's court, his love and collection of rare books of his father Shahrukh, Greek scientists Plato, Aristotle, Hipparchus, Menelaus, as well as being closely acquainted with the works of his compatriots Khorezmi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, and the presence of mature works on mathematics, astronomy and other sciences in Central Asia at that time. All these conditions led to the formation of the Ulugbek scientific direction and the creation of the "School of Astronomy" in Samarkand. One of the important scientific works of the Ulugbek school is the

astronomical tables called "Ulugbek Ziji" or "Zinj Koragoni". Zij consists of an introduction, i.e., a theoretical part, and tables based on the observations made at the Ulugbek observatory. There are calendar tables, trigonometric tables, planetary motion tables and star lists in 3 languages. Ulugbek's trigonometric tables were calculated to 10 decimal places. Many accountants were required to perform these tasks at a time when there were almost no calculators. Maybe a data center? Ulugbek's sine and cosine tables are compiled with one minute intervals. It was noted that Zijda Ulugbek wrote a separate treatise on calculating the sine of one degree. But this work of his has not been found yet. In the practical astronomy part of the book, there are issues such as the deviation of the ecliptic to the equator, determination of the coordinates of skylights, determination of geographic longitude and latitude of an arbitrary point on the earth, determination of distances between stars and planets. Grandfather moon and the sun eclipses two methods: O`zi made up tables using; Directly counting determination possible says and to methods circle examples brings Ulugbek's star list consists of 1018 stars, arranged by constellations. In addition to the number of each star in the constellation, a brief description of its position in the constellation, longitude and latitude relative to the equinox point in 1437 is given in the list. Astronomical works of the great scientist named "Risolai Ulug`bek" and historical works named "Tarihi Arba`ulus" have not been studied either. These works are well-known and unique in the history of

science. It should also be said that in the Muslim country and in general, in the Islamic culture, the exact sciences, especially agronomy and mathematics, are extremely important, because no matter where a Muslim is, five times of prayer from early morning to evening is obligatory for him. Prayer times are determined according to the height of the sun above the ground in each geographic latitude. In addition, the Hijri year accepted in Islam consists of 12 lunar months of 354 days, and the crescent moon is determined visually from the minaret of the mosque or from the top of the observatory. Therefore, the life of a Muslim is related to astronomy, mathematics, geography, crafts and architecture. Under the pressure of reactionary circles, Ulugbek's son Abdullatif executed his father near Samarkand in the fall of 1449 under the pretext of a trip to Mecca. Ulugbek's body was buried in Samarkand. After the tragic death of Ulugbek in 1449, the scholars of Samarkand gradually spread throughout the countries of the Middle East. They brought the achievements of Samarkand scientists and copies of "Zij" to the lands they visited. In particular, Ali Kushchi went to Istanbul in 1473 and built an observatory there. In this way, Ulugbek "Zij" spread in Turkey and reached European countries through Turkey. According to current information, there are about 120 Persian copies and more than 15 Arabic copies of "Zish", a famous Central Asian mathematician and astronomer.

His full name is Jamshid Ibn Masud Ibn Mahmud Ghiyasidin al Koshi. He died in

Samarkand around 1430. He is also called "Koshoni" because he was born in the city of Koshon, Iran. There is almost no information about Koshani's biography. According to the writings of some historians of mathematics, he received his primary education in his native city of Koshi. In the 15th century, Koshan was a very developed city. Together with his scientists, especially hand-made florists, he spread grain in the east. Like medieval scientists, Koshi was also involved in many fields of science. Among the subjects he was interested in was medicine. Koshi was invited by Ulugbek to work in his astronomy school. Scientific staff was needed for the School of Astronomy. Koshiy taught astronomy and mathematics at the Ulugbek madrasa. At the same time, he took part in the scientific work of the Ulugbek school. As a result of his scientific work, he created "The key to calculation", "Treatise on the circle", "Treatise on vatar and sine" and many other works. The discoveries made by Cauchy in the field of mathematics are huge. In his time, the number system of 60 was used for calculation needs. He was the first to discover decimals and showed the rules of performing operations on them. Cauchy's second discovery was the p-root operation of numbers. Through the works of Umar Khayyam, Koshi knew the formula for arbitrary natural powers and used it to extract natural power roots from arbitrary numbers. To the question whether this method did not exist before Kashi, the historian of mathematics P. Lukey says that this method is found in Ahmed al-Nasafi for finding cube roots. Lukey assumes that Umar Khayyam must have been engaged in

this method during the period between Nasafi and Koshi. But the generalization of this method for any natural p-s undoubtedly applies to Cauchy. Koshiy's "Treatise on the Circle" is dedicated to the calculation of the length of the circle in relation to its diameter, that is, the P-number. Scientists have been engaged in calculating the exact value of P since ancient times. Archimedes' method for calculating the Caustic P-ping value uses the drawing of two regular polygons on a circle. He calculated the perimeter of a regular (3.228) polygon and derived this value from the 2P ping hexadecimal number system. The third work of Koshiy - "Treatise on Vatar and Sinus" has not been found yet. But as mentioned in the work "Calculation key", this work of Cauchy is also one of the important problems of mathematics, which is dedicated to understanding the value of one third of the given arc and watar, and in the current definitions, to find $\sin 10$ from $\sin 30$. This method of trigonometry is very popular in mathematics. p related to issues. First, he $X^3 + g = rX$ in the form of cube of Eq integrated roots method calculation, secondly ancient classic matter corner trisection with As we mentioned above, Koshiy took an active part in the mathematical calculations carried out at the School of Astronomy of Ulugbek, and he wrote several works on astronomy. But his works have not reached us.

In conclusion, along with Al-Khorazmi, Ulug'bek, Farabi and many other scholars, Koshi also wrote a number of his works on mathematics. Ghiyasiddin Koshiy created not only works related to mathematics, but

also related to astronomy. He is interested in all subjects and learns them perfectly. Ghiyasiddin Koshi's works are still used today. Especially his mathematical works are very useful for mathematicians.

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